

Human-Robot Interface in Skills Acquisition and Delivery in Robotic Surgery

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INTRODUCTION:

The advent and exponential uptake of robotic platforms in the surgical field has ushered with it new challenges with the way humans interact with robots. This includes complex interplay of human-robot, human/human-robotic and robot-human feedback interfaces.

AIM:

To explore the human robot interface and to define characteristics inherent in surgical skills acquisition and delivery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Several novel platforms are explored and key concepts evaluated. The evaluation is permitted by systematic interrogation of novel leading edge concepts defined recently.

RESULTS:

Ten key interface platforms have been found. The roles of the concepts are defined in securing optimal skill acquisition and delivery in robotic surgery.

CONCLUSIONS:

The exponential increase in the uptake of robotic surgery demands a greater understanding of the human-robot interface. This is particularly critical where patients and lives are concerned. There is a greater need for further large-scale multicenter studies to further evaluate the current platforms.

KEYWORDS:

Robot; Human; Robotic; Surgery; Patients; Skills

BIOGRAPHY:

Dr Kommu is a specialist in the minimally invasive management of urological cancers including laparoscopic and robotic urological surgery. He is a member of all four colleges of The Royal College of Surgeons in the United Kingdom. He completed his Basic Surgical Training in the North West in England and has recently completed his training as a Specialist Registrar/ Urology Resident in the London Deanery in the United Kingdom. His academic interests are both clinical and basic sciences. His key clinical interests are in the minimally invasive treatment of urological cancers, surgical robotics and intelligent probes. He has done formal research at The Royal Marsden NHS Foundation Trust and The Institute of Cancer Research with The Translational Cancer Genetics Team where he refined his scientific methodology in advanced laboratory work with an emphasis on cancer genetics

and proteomics. He has also gained vast exposure in Nanotechnology. He has over 100 peer-reviewed publications in respected scientific and medical journals including The Lancet. He also has over 300 Scientific Presentations, several book chapters and books. Dr Kommu has over 25 academic awards including The Olympus Award at The 25th World Congress of Endourology in Cleveland U.S.A. 2006. He has nine patents pending including, a cost effective Telerounding Kit for Remote Teleconsultations, which was presented at The House of Commons (Hosted by The British Parliament) in 2006. His ability to blend medical science with engineering and technology has earned him two NASA collaborative scientific commendations. Dr Kommu is reviewer for 15 Surgical/Urological and 3 Basic Sciences Journals. Among several novel concepts described by Dr Kommu, include 'suppressor screening in urological cancer screening' and 'the supplementary biomarker approach' for detecting cancers.